

**METHODS OF ORGANIZING INDIVIDUAL TRAINING SESSIONS TO
DEVELOP THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE
DIRECTORS BASED ON LITERARY WORKS**

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Annotation. This article recommends methods for organizing individual training sessions aimed at enhancing students' individual capabilities in developing the professional competence of future directors based on literary works. The article also outlines the methodology for implementing each recommended method.

Keywords: art, director, literary work, individual, individual session, individual learning trajectory, method, methodology.

Introduction. The methodology of individual approaches and the development of an individual learning trajectory in the process of developing the professional competence of future directors based on literary works are pedagogical necessities. This involves creating conditions for the realization and enhancement of students' individual capabilities, individualizing educational activities, applying teaching methods that align with the student's personal characteristics through one-on-one sessions between the teacher and the student, reflecting on the results, and evaluating their activities to ensure the student's ability to work independently in the field.

Science does not stand still and constantly demands updates. For instance, there was a time when education widely used a general approach, teaching all students based on uniform, unchanging programs.

Today, however, many countries have actively transitioned to individual education, which is now being implemented at every stage of continuous education. This includes pre-school, school, higher education, and post-graduate stages, where

great attention is paid to developing individuality. This is also referred to as an educational trajectory in modern terms [5].

Educators' high level of knowledge in applying individual education is the most crucial tool, enabling them to observe all types of student development and provide adaptive solutions. According to statistics, when an average of 30% of students receive support from special programs during the first nine years of their education, the individual learning trajectory yields the expected results [2, 247].

Literature review and methodology. Numerous researchers have conducted studies on the methodology of organizing individual training sessions, focusing on selecting educational and instructional methods that align with the students' abilities and characteristics, thereby enhancing their individual potential. For instance, B.B. Baymetov and M. Sharipjanov have researched the methodology of providing individualized education to develop students' creative abilities in higher pedagogical education [1]. Sh.R. Samarova has examined exercises that encourage students' interest in learning through an individualized approach in the educational process [3], and these methodologies have been applied within the educational system.

The technology of individualized education is viewed as an approach that creates favorable opportunities for the learner and ensures the main goal of education-comprehensive and harmonious development of the learner's personality. In individualized education, the student is placed at the center of the educational process, and all components of the educational process are directed toward their learning and upbringing. Indeed, since the primary goal of the educational process is to educate, all available means and resources should be directed toward enhancing the student's personal and professional potential, bringing their knowledge, skills, and competencies to a competent level, thereby improving the quality and effectiveness of education [3, 824].

One of the most promising models for individualizing educational activities is the educational trajectory. Similar to other levels of education, the importance of

this method in higher education is steadily increasing. The educational trajectory is an individual form of realizing each student's personal potential in education, wherein the organizational, creative, and other personal abilities of students are identified and guided accordingly throughout the educational process. This means that each student is engaged individually based on their interests and professional aspirations [5].

Discussion and results. Utilizing an individual educational trajectory in developing the professional competence of future directors based on literary works offers distinct advantages. Notably, it encompasses not only the student's activities during classroom sessions but also their scientific and creative endeavors outside the classroom.

The primary focus of the individual educational trajectory and approach is organizing individual sessions aimed at developing the student's personal potential and talent. In current educational practice, individual sessions are referred to as one-on-one lessons, held once a week during a classroom session, typically lasting for one academic hour. The main goal of these individual sessions is to enhance the student's creative abilities based on the activities conducted both within and outside the classroom.

Recommended methods for organizing individual training sessions to develop the professional competence of future directors based on literary works:

Developing professional competence through the "Oral Storytelling" method:

The "Oral Storytelling" method is used during individual sessions by the course artistic director to develop the student's verbal skills and artistic thinking. This method represents the initial stage in shaping the student's storytelling abilities, where all processes are conducted orally.

The process of developing the professional competence of future directors through the "Oral Storytelling" method during individual sessions follows this

sequence: The "Oral Storytelling" method is dialogic in nature, involving the oral composition of a story. Initially, the course artistic director selects a topic for the future story. The student is provided with an understanding of story writing and the norms of literary language. After explaining the importance, procedure, and conditions of the "Oral Storytelling" method, the artistic director begins the story. Once a thought is expressed, the student continues it.

The "Oral Storytelling" progresses in this manner. After the story concludes, the course artistic director provides the student with methodological advice on the shortcomings observed during the oral storytelling process.

Developing professional competence through the "Logical Storytelling" method. The primary goal of the "Logical Storytelling" method is to enhance the student's artistic thinking and reasoning, broaden their worldview, develop their imagination and creativity, and improve their improvisation skills. Additionally, this method aims not to push students towards becoming playwrights but rather to provide them with a comprehensive understanding of the rules and principles of dramaturgy as authors.

The "Logical Storytelling" method is implemented as follows: First, during the individual session, the course artistic director engages in a creative discussion with the student about the genre of the story. This conversation covers what a story is, its unique genre characteristics, compositional structure, plot, conflict, and other dramatic requirements.

Developing Professional Competence of Future Directors through the "Continuous Story" Method:

The "Continuous Story" method enhances the student's improvisation skills, their ability to logically continue someone else's thoughts, quick-wittedness, depth of reasoning, and, most importantly, their artistic thinking and imagination. During individual sessions, the course artistic director recommends that the student read the

initial part of a less popular story, up to the point where the main events begin. The student repeatedly reads this introductory section and continues the story based on their own ideas and objectives. When continuing the story, the initial events and characters depicted by the author must be logically and coherently developed by the student.

Developing professional competence of future directors through the "Ikebana" method:

The "Ikebana" method is employed in individual sessions to develop the student's artistic worldview, artistic thinking, ability to express opinions on an event, independent thinking skills, and, most crucially for a director, their imagination. In Ikebana, a given composition conveys a specific meaning, often presenting itself as a unique, enigmatic state that isn't immediately apparent. Therefore, using the art of Ikebana is essential in developing the imagination and logical thinking of future directors. Since Ikebana is a form of enigmatic art and composition, the student must discern the meaning embedded within it.

In individual sessions with future directors, the use of enigmatic images, such as Ikebana, not only enhances their thinking and imagination but also increases their interest in the lesson and strengthens their artistic perspective. For this reason, students are provided with several Ikebana compositions, and they must decipher the meaning within each and build a narrative around a specific event.

Developing the professional competence of future directors through the "Cover" ("Muqova") method. The "Cover" method is recommended as a way to develop students' artistic thinking, expand their artistic worldview, and enrich their imagination through individual lessons. The "Cover" method is akin to the cover of a book, where the student must draw the cover of a literary work they have independently read.

During the individual lesson, under the guidance of the course's artistic director, the student draws portraits of all the characters from the literary work they have independently read (the drawings do not need to be of a professional level). The student provides information about each character's age, profession, personality, goals, and role in the story, as well as how the characters relate to each other. Following this, a creative discussion between the course's artistic director and the student about the literary work is held.

Developing the professional competence of future directors through the "Three Rings" method. The "Three Rings" method is essential for developing the writing skills of future directors and consists of three stages. The development of the student's writing ability is based on the principle of moving from simplicity to complexity: in the 1st year, they work on drabbles; in the 2nd year, on short stories; and in the 3rd year, on dramatic works. In this process:

– 1st year: The concept of drabbles is introduced. Students familiarize themselves with several drabbles. A plot is selected for writing a drabble, which is then written in story form. The story's content and form are optimized for brevity, while preserving the core essence of the narrative. After consulting with the course's artistic director, the final version of the drabble is written, with a focus on artistic quality and substance.

– 2nd year: The concept of a short story is introduced. A plot is selected, and based on this plot, the theme, idea, and purpose are defined. The characters are described. The composition structure and a preliminary version of the story are mentally prepared. The story must have a clear setting, time, character traits, language, and content. After the course's artistic director reads the story, appropriate recommendations are given, and revisions are made.

– 3rd year: Based on the experience gained from writing drabbles and short stories, it is recommended that students write a short one-act dramatic play. In this dramatic work, the characters' personalities should be clearly defined, the plot should

be concise, and it should be built around strong conflict. The characters' dialogue must align with their personalities, and the content and logic should complement each other. The student must ensure clarity in time and place, character consistency, and compositional artistry in the play. Every word and dramatic action should be carefully considered until the course's artistic director approves it.

It is important to note that in developing students' writing abilities, their individual capabilities must be taken into account. If a student lacks the initial elements of writing talent, it is recommended that they focus on staging work instead. However, if a student shows inherent qualities suited to writing, the process should begin with reading short literary works, followed by discussions and relevant recommendations. Students must diligently study the theory of literature and drama. Only after this should they be tested as writers or dramatists. Students who pass this test positively should be given opportunities to write drabbles, short stories, and dramatic works, with methodological guidance provided by the course's artistic director.

Moreover, in individual education, the teaching process should be organized based on the students' existing capabilities, talents, and potential, with maximum confidence placed in them.

Conclusion. Individual lessons are crucial for developing the professional competence of future directors based on literary works. The individual capabilities and talents of each student are nurtured throughout this process. In developing students' writing skills, it is essential first to consider their individual capabilities, ensure they have a solid understanding of the theory of literature and drama, and then provide opportunities for writing drabbles, short stories, and dramatic works, with ongoing methodological guidance from the course's artistic director.

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